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Missionaries' Leadership Styles as Determinants of Productivity in The Redeemed Christian Church of God Region-39, Ondo State

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Abstract

Productivity of missionaries is perceived to significantly influenced by the leadership styles (LSs) they adopt. Despite numerous studies on missionary work and training, there seems not to be many studies on the impact of leadership style on missionary productivity, particularly within the mission fields of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). Hence, this study investigated missionaries' leadership styles as determinants of productivity within the mission fields of the RCCG Region-39, Ondo State. The theoretical basis resides within transformational theory, and the *missio dei* theory. The study adopted descriptive survey research design, and simple random sampling technique was adopted to select 100 respondents. Data were collected using a duly-validated questionnaire ($r=0...$). Data was analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. Findings revealed that leadership style adopted by field missionaries of RCCG Region-39 includes laissez-faire leadership style, transformational leadership style, democratic leadership style, and servant leadership style, and that transformational and servant LSs has fostered growth among parishes established under RCCG Region-39, with increased church attendance (70%) facilitated a harmonious relationship between the church and the host community (75%) and led to rapid promotion among missionaries working in RCCG Region 39 (71%). Similarly, majority

of the respondents agreed that leadership style contributed to the growth of parishes (66%) and brought about increase in church attendance (71%). Moreover, findings revealed that majority of the respondents believed that the leadership style has improved the relationship between the church and the host community (66%) and also acknowledged the rapid promotion (75%) among missionaries. The study therefore, concludes that transformational leadership and servant leadership styles are mostly adopted and recommends that missionaries should embrace Transformational and Servant Leadership styles to enhance their missions field productivity within RCCG Region-39, and must recognize that leadership entails service.

Keywords: Leadership, Leadership Styles, Missionary, Redeemed Christian Church of God

Introduction

Leadership is a complex and intriguing concept that has garnered much attention from various fields, including philosophy, history, psychology, sociology, politics, and executive management. It is widely recognised as a fundamental function of management and has been extensively studied (Igboeli, 2010). In essence, leadership is the process of directing, guiding, and influencing individuals towards achieving group objectives. A leader is the central figure in this interaction, influencing their followers or group to attain a given objective. Followers may include superiors, peers, or subordinates of the leader (Ile, 2019). The willingness of individuals to follow is what defines a leader, with people gravitating towards those who provide a means of fulfilling their desires and needs. Effective leadership involves the use of various forms of power to influence followers' behaviour and entails taking responsibility for the achievement of group objectives. Trust and cooperation are crucial to ensure leadership success.

The significance of leadership has been extolled throughout history by exceptional leaders who are driven by their passion for their nation or humanity. Its impact can be either positive or negative. It can either build or break an organization, develop or obliterate a cause, or enable or stagnate an effort (Appleby, 2011). Biblical leadership provides a timeless example of leadership through the Old and New Testament

characters who embody "the heart's touch with God." Christian leadership is not a product of human creation or inheritance but is a calling from God to lead with Christlike character and demonstrate the competencies required for effective leadership. The fundamental elements of Christian leadership include being called by God, possessing Christlike character, and having functional competencies (Barna Group, 2020).

Leadership is the process through which an individual directs the behaviours of followers to achieve organizational goals. The followers perceive the influence of the leader as legitimate through either election or a position in the organizational structure. This understanding of leadership assigns a pivotal role to the leader in the organization, granting them various powers to fulfil their responsibility of guiding others towards achieving the stated goals. The success of the leader critically depends not only on their abilities and skills but also on their behaviours, i.e., the actions they take to influence followers towards achieving organizational goals.

It is imperative for a leader to establish and uphold a favourable work atmosphere in accordance with the organizational culture and to the contentment of their employees. This may seem like an ideal situation, as many workers frequently endure unfavourable conditions at the hands of their leaders due to minimal effort towards creating a work environment conducive to the betterment of their employees' lives, despite their invested energy and efforts. Poor leaders often promote their image by taking credit for others' work, exhibiting selfish, inconsiderate, or tyrannical behaviour towards their followers, or displaying unfair, dishonest, and threatening tendencies towards competent individuals. These factors greatly reduce quality of life, lowering job and life satisfaction, and commitment to the organization, while simultaneously creating heightened levels of conflict and stress (Barna Group, 2020).

Leadership amongst church leaders in Africa is heavily influenced by cultural values, traditional and political leaders who advocate for lifelong power. The primary concern is whether the church leader is influenced by their environment when selecting their leadership style or succumbs to the temptation of being influenced by a dictatorial environment, where individuals manipulate constitutions, leading their countries into civil war, prepare their children to replace them, or even appoint them

by force. Leaders are expected to come to power through legitimate means, within the framework of policies or constitutions. Upon obtaining power, leaders are expected to improve the livelihood of citizens, practice equity and fairness for all, and make tangible advancements in democracy, human rights, socio-economic, and educational development. A church leader is expected to exhibit Christian values at a high level and, as a messenger of God, adopt a servant leadership style. The premise being made is that church leaders should set a good example for church members, communities, societies, and political leaders to follow.

Leaders are responsible for creating and sustaining a positive work climate, by establishing appropriate organizational structures, implementing good policies, and adopting effective leadership styles that positively impact organizational performance and productivity. There have been allegations that some men and women of God in church leadership positions do not do enough to create a favourable work environment in conferences, missions, hospitals, schools, and other church institutions. However, the extent of this alleged misbehaviour and its causes remain unknown. Some pastors or employees seek personal transfer to other conferences or missions because they are uncomfortable working in their respective home conferences in the country.

It is of utmost importance that Christians uphold "the unity of the faith" (Ephesians 4:3) and equally essential that they strive to preserve the unity of the spirit in the bond of peace. Such unity necessitates prudence and consultation with ecclesiastical authorities. God is guiding people out of the world onto the elevated platform of eternal truth, God's commandments, and the faith of Jesus. He shall discipline and prepare His followers⁵. The scripture says; "moreover, you shall select from the people able men, such as fear God, men of truth, hating covetousness, and place such over them to be rulers of thousands, rulers of hundreds, rulers of fifties, and rulers of tens" (Exodus 18:21). Similarly Acts 6:3 instructs, "therefore, brethren seek out from among seven men of good reputation, full of the holy spirit and wisdom, whom we may appoint over this business." Correspondingly, 1 Timothy 3:7 expounds on church leadership, "moreover, he must have a good testimony among those who are outside, lest he falls into reproach and snare of the devil."

A missionary is an individual who has been summoned by God to proclaim the gospel to unreached people and establish churches. While God calls missionaries, proper training remains indispensable in the work of missions. Jesus Christ exemplified this by training His disciples for over three years before sending them to the mission field. Today, some posit that missionaries require no training before embarking on the mission field, while others opine that missionaries should undergo brief training before deployment, confident in the Holy Spirit's support. Missionaries often find themselves in positions of leadership in the organizations they launch or join, whether in a pioneering church plant, a missionary team, a mission organization, an association of national churches, or even a sending church. Sometimes, these leadership endeavours succeed, while other times, results are suboptimal.

Productivity is a metric that quantifies the efficiency of the production process. It is computed by comparing the output to the inputs utilized in the production process, that is, the output per unit of input. When the productivity measure factors in all inputs and outputs, it is referred to as total productivity. In the total productivity measure, outputs and inputs are defined by their economic values. The difference between the value of outputs and inputs is an indicator of the income generated in the production process, thus representing the total efficiency of the production process. The maximization of productivity is the ultimate goal of any production process. Partial productivity refers to productivity measures that utilize one or more inputs or factors but not all of them. Labour productivity, which is calculated as output per hour, is a typical example of partial productivity. At the company level, partial productivity is measured by indicators such as worker hours, materials, or energy per unit of production.

The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) is a Bible-based church that emphasizes proper conduct and moral behaviour through its teachings and missionary approach. Its vision is to spread the word of God to the ends of the earth (Matthew 28:18-20). The founder, Reverend Josiah Akindayomi, established the church in 1952, and it has been led by the present General Overseer, Pastor Enoch Adejare Adeboye, since Akindayomi's passing in 1981. The RCCG appeals to diverse people worldwide, with a determination to reach individuals in different geographical areas, secular stages of life, and spiritual levels of development. Currently, the RCCG has over 35,000 parishes globally

and is present in 197 countries, with established mission fields in Africa, Europe, Asia, the United States of America, the Caribbean, Canada, South America, Australia, and the Ocean/Pacific region. The RCCG is the most renowned and fastest-growing denomination in Africa (Ukah, 2008).

The constitution of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) mandates the establishment of a Bible School to train Mission officers. Attendance at the Bible School is a prerequisite for assuming office as a Mission officer unless an exemption is granted by the General Superintendent. The RCCG has three institutions devoted to the spiritual growth and development of its members: the Redeemed Christian Bible College, the School of Disciples, and the Redeemed College of Missions (Aiyedogbon, 2010). The focus of this paper is the Redeemed College of Missions, which specializes in training missionaries. This institution was created in 1993 as a subdivision of the Redeemed Christian Bible College but has since grown to become a standalone establishment located in Ede, Osun State, Nigeria. The Redeemed College of Missions is open to candidates of all denominations and mission agencies and provides advanced training in cross-cultural missions (RCCG Central Missions Board, 2022).

RCCG's missions policy requires that the cost of sending or sponsoring missionaries be carefully considered. The sponsoring entity may be an RCCG Province (either local or international) or the African Missions Global (AMG). Missionaries should be aware that they may be transferred within or outside of their primary region of assignment, in compliance with the policies of the host nation. The missions policy of the RCCG plays a crucial role in guiding the activities of missionaries, and this research aims to assess the impact of leadership styles on the productivity of missionaries in RCCG Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria (RCCG Central Missions Board, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

The productivity of missionaries is significantly influenced by the leadership styles they adopt. Despite numerous studies on missionary work and training, there is a lack of research on the impact of leadership style on missionary productivity, particularly within the confines of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). As one of the rapidly expanding Pentecostal churches in Africa, the RCCG boasts the highest

number of missionaries under its missions (Ukah, 2008). Therefore, it is imperative to investigate the leadership styles of missionaries as determinants of productivity in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region-39, Ondo State.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to assess the effects of leadership styles on the productivity of missionaries on the missions field. The objectives are to:

1. ascertain the extent to which leadership styles adopted by the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region-39 has enhances their productivity in the missions field.
2. appraise the relationship between leadership styles adopted and productivity among missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent to which leadership styles are deployed by missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Region 39, Ondo State?
2. What is the relationship between leadership styles adopted and productivity among missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39, Ondo State?

Theories

Transformational Theory: Transformational leadership stands out from previous and contemporary theories due to its dedication to the greater good. This dedication involves the followers in processes related to personal factors within the organisation and a course that generates superior social dividends. Transformational leaders increase the motivation and morality of both followers and themselves. It is believed that transformational leaders engage in interactions with followers based on common values, beliefs, and goals. This interaction positively impacts performance, leading to the attainment of goals. Transformational leadership involves leaders who inspire and motivate their followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes. This style of leadership is particularly effective in dynamic and challenging contexts

where a vision and a sense of purpose can drive innovation and change (Bass, 2017).

Missio Dei Theory: Missio Dei theory, translated from Latin as the "Mission of God," is a perspective in Christian theology that emphasizes God as the primary actor in mission. Unlike some other theories that focus on the church or individual missionaries, the missio dei theory places God at the centre of the mission, asserting that the mission is an extension of God's nature and purpose in the world. The missio dei theory starts with the premise that mission is fundamentally God's initiative and activity in the world. God's mission is seen as comprehensive and all-encompassing, involving the redemption and restoration of all creation. Missio Dei encompasses a holistic understanding of the mission. It includes not only evangelism and the salvation of individuals but also addresses social, economic, and ecological aspects of life. The mission is seen as comprehensive, involving the transformation of the whole person and society (Olafare, 2023).

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study and the research design was considered appropriate because the study involved the collection of data to objectively describe existing phenomena, without any manipulation or randomization. Also, the research design allowed the researcher to obtain a true picture of the present condition of the particular phenomena under study. A total number of one hundred (100) respondents were selected from the two hundred and fifty (250) targeted missionaries using simple random sampling technique. Consequently, a total of twenty (20) missionaries were chosen from five (5) Provinces in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria. The five (5) Provinces are the Redeemed Christian Church of God Ondo Province 2, the Redeemed Christian Church of God Ondo Province 5, the Redeemed Christian Church of God Ondo Province 6, the Redeemed Christian Church of God Ondo Province 10, and the Redeemed Christian Church of God Ondo Province 12.

Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into five sections which were divided into two sections. Section A contained the demographic variables such as gender, age, years of ministerial experience, and province of the respondent. Section

B contained 25 items on a 4-point scoring scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Data was analysed using frequency counts and percentage. Table 1 presents the demographic information of respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Repondents (N=100)

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	80	80%
	Female	20	20%
Age	20 – 30	20	20%
	31 – 40	30	30%
	41 – 50	39	39%
	Above 50	11	11%
Highest Qualification	SSCE	2	2%
	OND/NCE	16	16%
	B.SC/HND	48	48%
	M.SC/PHD	34	34%
Marital Status	Single	38	38%
	Married	61	61%
	Divorced	-	-
	Widowed	1	1%
Province	Ondo 2	20	20%
	Ondo 5	20	20%
	Ondo 6	20	20%
	Ondo 10	20	20%
	Ondo 12	20	20%

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 presents the demographic data analysis which shows the gender, age, marital status, highest qualification, and the province of each respondent. The table reveals that a total number of 80 are males representing 80% while 20 representing 20% are females. The age range

is 20-30 years and 51 years and above. Marital status and province comprised.

Results and Findings

Research Question One: What is the extent to which leadership styles are adopted by missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Region 39, Ondo State?

Table 2: Leadership Style Adopted by Missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria Affect their Performance (N=100)

S/N	Items	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
1.	The leadership style in Region 39 promotes healthy conflict resolution and also maintains a harmonious working environment which prevents conflicts from affecting performance negatively. Missionaries are more likely to be enthusiastic and dedicated in their work, as a result of the leadership style adopted and	29 (29%)	41 (41%)	16 (16%)	14 (14%)
2.		16 (16%)	43 (43%)	27 (27%)	14 (14%)

	this has positively impacted their performance				
3.	The growth of the church both numerically and spiritually depends on the type of leadership styles operated by the missionaries	20 (20%)	40 (40%)	38 (38%)	2 (2%)
4.	Effective leaders provide a clear vision and direction for the missionaries working in RCCG Region 39	36 (36%)	39 (39%)	7 (7%)	18 (18%)
5.	Missionaries working in Region 39 who feel cared for and supported by their leaders perform effectively in their missions field	16 (16%)	44 (44%)	24 (24%)	16 (16%)

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows that 70 participants (70%) concurred with the assertion that "the leadership style in RCCG Region 39 promotes effective conflict resolution and maintains a harmonious working environment, thereby preventing conflicts from adversely affecting performance," whereas 30 participants (30%) expressed disagreement. This demonstrates that effective conflict resolution and a harmonious environment are dependent on the leadership style embraced by missionaries. Additionally, 59 participants (59%) agreed with the assertion that

"missionaries are more likely to exhibit enthusiasm and dedication in their work as a result of the leadership style adopted, which positively impacts their performance," while 41 participants (41%) disagreed. This implies that the performance of missionaries is positively influenced by the leadership style adopted by these missionaries.

Once again, 60 participants (60%) agreed with the assertion that "the growth of the church, both in terms of numerical and spiritual aspects, hinges on the type of leadership styles practised by the missionaries," whereas 40 participants (40%) disagreed. This confirms that leadership style significantly contributes to the numerical and spiritual growth of the church. Similarly, 75 participants (75%) agreed with the assertion that "effective leaders provide a clear vision and direction for the missionaries working in RCCG Region 39," while 25 participants (25%) disagreed. This indicates that missionaries require effective leadership to have a clear vision and direction for their ministry. Finally, 60 participants (60%) agreed with the assertion that "missionaries working in RCCG Region 39 who feel cared for and supported by their leaders perform effectively in their mission field," while 40 participants (40%) disagreed. This demonstrates that for missionaries to perform effectively in their respective mission fields, particularly in RCCG Region 39, they must receive proper care and support from their leaders.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between leadership styles adopted and productivity among missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39, Ondo State?

Table 3: Relationship between Leadership Styles and Productivity Among Missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria

S/ N	Items	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
1.	Laissez-faire leadership style among missionaries leads to lower	36 (36%)	41 (41%)	16 (16%)	7 (7%)

	productivity in less experienced or motivated missionaries				
	Missionaries under transformational leaders show higher levels of productivity due to their leaders' ability to instil enthusiasm, commitment, and a shared vision in them				
2.	Missionaries who adopt the democratic style of leadership are slow in decision-making processes because it involves team members in decision-making	41 (41%)	45 (45%)	7 (7%)	7 (7%)
3.	Servant leaders among missionaries lead to positive productivity because their well-being and development are prioritized	29 (29%)	60 (60%)	9 (9%)	2 (2%)
4.		41 (41%)	45 (45%)	9 (9%)	5 (5%)

Missionaries					
5.	who feel cared for and supported are likely to be more engaged, motivated, and productive in their mission work	41 (41%)	43 (43%)	5 (5%)	11 (11%)

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 presents finding on research question two which revealed that; 77 participants (77%) agreed that the laissez-faire leadership style among missionaries leads to reduced productivity in less experienced or motivated missionaries, whereas 23 participants (23%) disagreed. This suggests that the laissez-faire leadership style should not be employed among missionaries, as it hampers productivity among missionaries who are new to the ministry or lack motivation. Furthermore, 86 participants (86%) agreed that missionaries under transformational leaders exhibit higher levels of productivity due to their leaders' ability to instill enthusiasm, commitment, and a shared vision in them, while 14 participants (14%) disagreed. This indicates that the adoption of transformational leadership by missionaries results in heightened productivity levels.

Furthermore, the finding revealed that the majority of respondents (89%) concurred that the democratic style of leadership embraced by missionaries is associated with sluggishness in decision-making processes due to the involvement of team members. Conversely, 11% of respondents expressed disagreement with this notion. This indicates that the adoption of democratic leadership within the missionary context leads to decreased productivity as it hampers the expeditiousness of decision-making, consequently impeding the productivity of missionaries. Similarly, a significant number of respondents (86%) agreed that servant leadership among missionaries yields positive productivity due to the prioritization of their well-being and development. On the other hand, 14% of respondents expressed dissent.

This implies that servant leadership contributes to favourable productivity among missionaries, thereby suggesting that missionaries should consider adopting this leadership style. Lastly, a considerable proportion of respondents (84%) agreed that when missionaries feel cared for and supported, they are more likely to be engaged, motivated, and productive in their mission work. In contrast, 16% of respondents disagreed. This demonstrates that when missionaries receive proper care and ample support, they exhibit enhanced productivity in their respective mission fields.

Discussion of the Findings

Finding on research question one regarding leadership style adopted by missionaries in RCCG Region-39, Ondo State, Nigeria and its effects on their productivity revealed that there has been effective conflict resolution and the establishment of a harmonious working environment among missionaries in RCCG Region 39, as attested to by 70% of respondents. Furthermore, missionaries have displayed enthusiasm and dedication towards their work, which has positively impacted their performance, as affirmed by 59% of respondents. Additionally, 60% of respondents acknowledged that the numerical and spiritual growth of the church depends on the type of leadership styles employed by the missionaries. Lastly, 60% of respondents agreed that missionaries working in RCCG Region 39 who feel cared for and supported by their leaders exhibit effective performance in their mission fields. These findings suggest that missionaries in RCCG Region 39, Ondo State perform exceptionally well due to the leadership style they have adopted. Further, finding on research question two revealed that laissez-faire leadership style among missionaries is associated with decreased productivity in less experienced or motivated missionaries, with 77% of the respondents agreeing. On the other hand, 86% of the respondents acknowledged that missionaries under transformational leaders exhibit higher levels of productivity due to their leaders' ability to inspire enthusiasm, commitment, and a shared vision. Additionally, 89% of the respondents believed that missionaries who adopt a democratic style of leadership tend to have slower decision-making processes due to the involvement of team members in decision-making. Similarly, 86% of the respondents supported the notion that servant leaders among missionaries contribute to positive productivity as they prioritize the

well-being and development of their followers. Lastly, regarding research question three, 84% of the respondents agreed that missionaries who feel cared for and supported are more likely to be engaged, motivated, and productive in their mission work. This suggests a strong relationship between the leadership style employed by missionaries in RCCG Region 39 and their productivity in the missions field, as the missionary's actions heavily rely on the leadership style they have adopted.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings, the study concludes that the most effective leadership styles for missionaries in RCCG Region 39 are transformational and servant leadership styles. These styles contribute to the increased productivity of missionaries in the missions field. However, democratic leadership style also has its merits, although it can slow down decision-making processes that have the potential to enhance the performance of missionaries. On the other hand, laissez-faire leadership style among missionaries leads to decreased productivity. Furthermore, the missionaries affiliated with the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria have displayed exceptional performance, which can be attributed to the leadership style adopted by these missionaries. Additionally, there has been a noticeable increase in the establishment of new parishes, church attendance, a harmonious relationship between the church and the local community, and rapid career advancement among missionaries working in RCCG Region 39, Ondo State, Nigeria, due to the leadership style implemented by the missionaries.

Recommendations

In light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To enhance their productivity in the missions field, missionaries in the Redeemed Christian Church of God Region 39 should consider embracing transformational and servant leadership styles.
2. It is crucial to approach church leadership by biblical principles, as the church is God's enterprise rather than that of men. Therefore, church leadership must adhere to God's prescribed formula.
3. Missionaries must recognize that leadership entails service.

Consequently, any missionary who considers themselves too important to serve should not be entrusted with the responsibility of leading.

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